

Water Pollution in Ken River of Banda District Uttar Pradesh,

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Banda is the easternmost district of Bundelkhand region. It lies between latitude 24°53' and 24°55' North and longitude 80°27' and 81°34' East with the area of 7,624 sq.km. The western boundary of Banda touches Chhatarpur and Hamirpur districts separated by river ken for certain distance. In present investigation the physicochemical characteristic of Ken river were studied, water samples were collected quarterly for five different sites of Ken river during the year January 2024 to December 2025. Preservation and analysis of water samples were based on standard method proposed by American public Health Association (APHA 2005) in cationic abundance sodium is followed by calcium magnesium and potassium (Na>Ca>Mg>K) in the river through out of year. The tolerance limit for TDS, SAR and % Na of water use for irrigation has been found to be excellent for TDS and % Na, fair for SAR. Nitrate sulphat and phosphate were found to below the permission limit of WHO (1993).

Keywords: TDS, SAR, Anthropogenic Nanogram, Microgram.

Introduction

The surface water quality is a matter of serious concern today. River due to their role in carrying off the municipal and industrial wastewater and run off from agricultural land in their vast drainage basins are among the most vulnerable water bodies to pollution (yerel 2010). water pollution has now reached a crisis point specifically in developing world. Almost every water body is polluted to an alarming level. Thus, estimation of quality of water is extremely important for proper assessment of the associated hazards (warhate et al 2006) aquatic ecosystem are not only source of water and resources, such as fish and crop for household and agro industrial uses, but are vital parts of natural environment on which economic system are parasites and depend for their survival (Rai and Pal 2001).

Aquatic ecosystem are getting polluted day by day due to growth of the industrial corridor, nutrient loading and rapid anthropogenic activities especially in developing countries due to addition of domestic waste (sewage), phosphate, nitrate etc from wastes or their decomposition products in water bodies, they become rich in nutrients, especially phosphates and nitrate ions. Thus with the passage of these nutrients through such organic wastes, the water bodies become highly productive or eutropic and the phenomenon as eutrophication in lake which is increasing day by day. The oxygen content of lake a also low due to oxygen depletion waste generated by anthropogenic activities (Kumar et at 2010).

In natural aquatic ecosystem, metallic compounds use to occur in low concentration, normally at nanogram to microgram per liter level. Heavy metals may come from natural sources, leached from rocks and soils according to their geochemical mobility or come from anthropogenic sources at the result of human land occupation and industrial pollution (Espinoza quinones et at 2005)

Industrial discharge variety of pollutants in the waste water including heavy metals, organic toxins, oil nutrients and solids. Many of the substances are toxic or even carcinogenic pathogens can obviously produce water born diseases in either human or animal hosts. These wastes also increase the concentration of suspended solid (turbidity), bacteria and virus growth leading to potential health impacts increase in nutrients load may lead to

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eutrophication; organic wastes increase the oxygen demand in water leading to oxygen reduction in water with potentially severe impacts on whole ecosystem (Yadav and Rajesh 2011). Therefore now a days fresh water has become a scare commodity due to over exploitation and pollution (Gupta et al 2009) with this background present proposed study has been undertaken form examine the water quality of river ken in Banda district.

Material and Methods

This is easternmost district of Bundelkhand Banda lies between latitude 24°53' and 24°55' North and longitude 80°27' and 81°34' East with an area of 7,624 sq.k. The southern and south eastern boundary of the district is made up of plateau and the mountain of vindhya bordering on the district Rewa, Satna, and Panna. the northern boundary is entirely made up by Yamuna River which flows for nearly 215 km, separating it from Fatehpur and Allahabad districts. The western boundary of Banda touches Chhatarpur and Hamirpur districts separated by river ken for certain distance.

Water samples were collected quarterly from five different sites from ken river (Figure-1) during the year 2024 & 2025 screw-capped high density pre-sterilized polypropylene bottles of one liter capacity, Labeled properly and analyzed in the Laboratory. Preservation and analysis method proposed by American Public Health Association (APHA 2005). pH, EC, TDS, Temperature and do were analyzed on the spot by water quality analyzer kit (Elico, PE 138) NO₃, PO₄ and SO₄ were analyzed by UV visible spectrophotometer (Elico, SL 159) Na and K were analyzed by flame photometer (systronic 130). The water quality was tested for it's use for irrigation and interpreted in terms of sodium absorption ratio (SAR) and % Na.

The tolerance limits for same parameters recommended by wilcox (1965) are given below. The Na% describing the sodium hazard giving the (warhate et al 2006)

$$\% \text{Na} = \frac{1 \times N^+}{(N^+ + C^+ + K^+ + M^+)}$$

The sodium or Alkali hazard in the use of water for irrigation is determined by absolute and relative concentration of cation and is expressed in terms of sodium absorption ratio (SAR) and it can be estimated by formula (Singh 2002).

$$\text{SAR} = \frac{N^+}{[(C^+ + M^+)/2]^{1/2}}$$

Where, concentrations are expressed in milli equivalent per litre (meq/l)

Map showing Sampling site at Ken River Banda

Fig. No. -1

Result and Discussion

The physico-chemical analysis carried out in quarterly for five different site of Ken River water during the year 2024 and 2025 are given in Table-2 and Table-3. The temperature plays a crucial role in physical-chemical and biological behaviour of aquatic system (Dwivedi and Pathak 2007). A study revealed that temperature varied from 19°C (in winter season) and 30°C (in summer seasons). Average temperature in both the year found to be 24°C. Higher values of pH fasten the scale formation in water heating apparatus and reduce germicidal potential of chlorine (Vijaya et al, 2002). It was observed that water is slightly alkaline in nature. The average pH value was found to be 7.5. The total hardness is mainly due to Ca, Mg and eutrophication. The water containing excess hardness is not desirable for potable water. It consumes more soap during washing of clothes. In the present study average value of hardness was found in 230 mg/l. Electrical conductivity is considered to be a rapid and good measure of dissolved solids conductivity is an important criterion in determining the suitability of water for irrigation (Gubtal et al 2009). The conductivity mainly depends on ionic concentration or dissolved inorganic substances (Zaidi et al 2011). The average value of electrical conductivity in both the year was found to be 730 µs/cm. Alkalinity is due to the presence of bicarbonate, carbonates or hydroxides (Trivedi and Goel 1992). The weathering of rocks is the potential source of alkalinity. The average value of alkalinity was found to be 190 mg/l in both the year. TDS indicates the general nature of salinity of water. Water with high TDS produces scales on cooking vessels and boilers. Water containing more than 500 mg/l of TDS is not considered suitable for drinking water supplies (Gupta et al, 2009). According to Wilcox (1965) classification (Table-1) the TDS value of Ken River was found to be excellent for irrigation use i.e. less than 200ppm. The main sources of dissolved oxygen in water are diffusion of oxygen from air and photosynthetic activity taking place in water. The diffusion of oxygen from air mainly dependent on temperature salinity, total dissolved salt and water movement etc (Zaidi et al 2011). The maximum value of DO in the month of January to March (14.5 mg/l) and minimum 10.2 mg/l in the month of April to June. Biochemical oxygen demand is usually defined as the amount of oxygen required by bacteria in stabilizing the decomposable organic matter. BOD gives an idea about the extent of pollution (Yadav and Rajesh, 2011; Jain et al 1996).

The BOD value was maximum (14.2 mg/l) in January to March and minimum (8.6 mg/l) in the month of April to June. The average value of BOD was found to be 10 mg/l. The chemical oxygen demand (COD) is a measure of oxygen equivalent to the requirement of oxidizing organic matter contents by a strong chemical agent. The COD test is helpful in indicating toxic conditions and the presence of biologically resistant organic substances. The maximum value (78 mg/l) of COD was found in July to September and minimum value (43 mg/l) in the month of January to March. The average value of COD was found to be 62 mg/l. The main sources of nitrate in water are human and animal waste, industrial effluent, use of fertilizers and chemicals, silage through drainage system (Jain et al 1991) was found under the permissible limit of WHO 1993 and BIS 1991 the Ken River water throughout the year (Table-2 and 3). The SAR and %Na of water use for irrigation recommended by Wilcox (1965). The data has been found to be excellent for TDS and %Na and fair for SAR.

Classification	TDS (ppm)	SAR	Na %
Excellent	<200	<10	<20
Good	200-500	10-18	20-40
Fair	500-1500	18-26	40-60
Unsuitable	>1500	>26	>60

Physico chemical properties of Ken River during the year 2024

Sa mpl e No.	p H	E C	Te m p	Tota l Har dnes s	Alka linity	T D S	D O	B O D	C O D	N O 3	P O 4	S O 4	N a	K	C a	M g	% Na	S A R
1	7.7 1 ± 0.5	7.3 4 ± 0.5	24.75 ± 1.1	230 ± 3.57	191 ± 2.23	18.7 ± 2.66	1.2 ± 0.44	9.6 ± 0.72	60.0 ± 3.90	3.9 ± 1.45	4.1 ± 0.33	87.5 ± 1.73	1.7 ± 0.24	4.5 ± 0.15	63.5 ± 1.79	2.3 ± 1.10	6.57 ± 0.10	23.9 ± 0.26
2	7.7 1 ± 0.5	7.3 0 ± 0.5	24.13 ± 1.1	231 ± 3.44	190 ± 2.17	18.9 ± 2.60	1.2 ± 0.43	10.4 ± 0.71	64.7 ± 3.78	3.6 ± 1.39	3.6 ± 0.34	85.6 ± 1.74	1.6 ± 0.28	3.8 ± 0.15	63.0 ± 1.77	2.5 ± 1.05	6.61 ± 0.10	24.1 ± 0.26
3	7.7 8 ± 0.5	7.3 4 ± 0.7	24.25 ± 1.1	236 ± 3.43	189 ± 2.20	18.9 ± 2.63	1.3 ± 0.43	10.5 ± 0.67	59.2 ± 3.70	3.7 ± 1.40	3.3 ± 0.33	90.1 ± 1.68	1.8 ± 0.21	3.8 ± 0.15	62.7 ± 1.67	2.3 ± 1.05	6.56 ± 0.09	24.0 ± 0.25
4	7.6 5 ± 0.5	7.1 8 ± 0.6	25.00 ± 1.0	237 ± 3.34	191 ± 2.12	18.5 ± 2.81	1.2 ± 0.41	10.0 ± 0.62	61.7 ± 3.51	4.2 ± 1.23	3.6 ± 0.31	93.6 ± 1.68	1.5 ± 0.24	3.7 ± 0.14	62.5 ± 1.63	2.4 ± 1.03	6.54 ± 0.09	24.1 ± 0.26
5	7.7 1 ± 0.5	7.3 3 ± 0.6	25.00 ± 1.0	234 ± 3.37	190 ± 2.11	19.1 ± 2.67	1.2 ± 0.40	10.0 ± 0.59	63.5 ± 3.36	4.1 ± 1.12	3.3 ± 0.22	92.8 ± 1.64	1.8 ± 0.19	3.8 ± 0.14	62.7 ± 1.50	2.5 ± 0.97	6.62 ± 0.08	23.8 ± 0.25

Physico chemical properties of Ken River during the year 2025

Sa mpl e	p H	E C	Te m p	Tota l Har	Alka linity	T D S	D O	B O D	C O D	N O 3	P O 4	S O 4	N a	K	C a	M g	% Na	S A R
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No.				dnes s														
1	7. 7 1 ± 0. 5	7 2 9 ± 8. 4	24. 25 ± 1.9 2	231 ± 3.48	192 ± 1.78	19 0 ± 2. 58	1 2. 5 ± 0. 3 6	10 .2 ± 0. 69	63 .7 ± 4. 22	4 0. 2 ± 1. 3 1	4. 1 ± 0. 3 0	87 ± 1. 48	1 5 8 ± 2. 3 8	3. 9 ± 0. 1 2	66 .0 ± 1. 92	2 4 ± 1. 1 5	6.6 8 ± 0.1 0	23 .6 ± 0. 28
2	7. 6 8 ± 0. 5	7 3 1 ± 9. 5	24. 12 ± 1.9 1	230 ± 3.26	190 ± 1.78	19 1 ± 2. 36	1 2. 6 ± 0. 3 6	10 .3 ± 0. 67	67 .2 ± 4. 09	3 9. 7 ± 1. 2 6	3. 7 ± 0. 3 1	87 ± 1. 44	1 6 3 ± 2. 2 3	4. 1 ± 0. 1 1	64 .2 ± 1. 88	2 6 ± 1. 0 1	6.7 1 ± 0.1 0	24 .2 ± 0. 29
3	7. 7 3 ± 0. 5	7 2 8 ± 1 0	24. 00 ± 1.8 9	238 ± 3.20	188 ± 1.92	19 4 ± 2. 30	1 2. 9 ± 0. 3 6	10 .3 ± 0. 64	63 .2 ± 3. 96	3 9. 9 ± 1. 2 9	3. 9 ± 0. 3 0	90 ± 1. 34	1 6 3 ± 2. 0 6	4. 2 ± 0. 1 1	64 .0 ± 1. 81	2 6 ± 1. 0 2	6.7 1 ± 0.0 9	24 .2 ± 0. 29
4	7. 6 7 ± 0. 5	7 2 5 ± 1 7	24. 50 ± 1.8 6	240 ± 3.12	190 ± 1.96	19 2 ± 2. 25	1 2. 7 ± 0. 3 5	10 .1 ± 0. 61	64 .0 ± 3. 71	4 3. 5 ± 1. 0 9	3. 9 ± 0. 9 9	94 ± 1. 31	1 6 3 ± 1. 9 8	4. 0 ± 0. 1 1	64 .5 ± 1. 77	2 3 ± 1. 0 3	6.5 9 ± 0.0 9	24 .7 ± 0. 29
5	7. 6 7 ± 0. 5	7 2 6 ± 1 4	24. 87 ± 1.8 1	240 ± 3.12	190 ± 1.92	19 2 ± 2. 09	1 2. 6 ± 0. 3 5	10 .5 ± 0. 59	64 .7 ± 3. 55	4 3. 2 ± 1. 0 5	3. 8 ± 0. 2 7	92 ± 1. 32	1 6 2 ± 1. 9 4	4. 2 ± 0. 1 0	66 .7 ± 1. 70	2 4 ± 1. 0 3	6.7 2 ± 0.0 9	24 .1 ± 0. 27

Conclusion

The nature water bodies are continuously getting contaminated by the discharge of sewage, industrial and other wastes originated from anthropogenic activities in and around the both of the lakes. The water quality and pollution of surface water disrupts algae communities which can affect the entire aquatic food web that will result is a serious threat of life (Rai and Pal 2001).

It is concluded that water quality of Ken River such as pH, alkalinity, hardness, Na, Nitrate, were found to be within WHO and BIS permissible limits. Therefore water of there dams can be used for irrigation purpose. The cationic chemistry is dominated by sodium (Na) and Calcium (Ca). According to Wilcox (1965) TDS & %Na is excellent sand fair for SAR that means it is suitable for agricultural purposes.

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